

**Travelling Pavlovism: ideas on children's development and on preschool education in Bulgaria and the GDR in the 1950s:
Prof. Eva Schmidt-Kolmer and Prof. Sophia Avramova**

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Abstract: *From the early 1950s onward, the teachings of Ivan Petrovich Pavlov on Higher Nervous Activity were incorporated into scientific policy across the USSR and other Eastern Bloc countries. After the 'Pavlovian Session' in Moscow in 1950 this influence extended to fields such as medicine, psychiatry, pedagogy, and sports science. However, the theoretical and practical reception of Pavlov's ideas varied significantly between countries. These differences were shaped by the prevailing scientific paradigms, the personal backgrounds of individual scholars, and the degree of political pressure they faced. Pavlovism had a notable impact on early childhood education, particularly because the 1950s marked a period of rapid expansion of the preschool system across socialist countries, driven largely by the increasing participation of women in the workforce. This context sets the stage for a comparison between activities and publications of two leading figures in preschool education: Professor Sofia Avramova (1900–1978) from Bulgaria and Professor Eva Schmidt-Kolmer (1913–1991) from the German Democratic Republic (GDR). Both women were activists in the Communist movement prior to World War II and later held prominent positions in the field of pedagogy. In the 1950s, they both embraced Pavlov's concept of Higher Nervous Activity as the scientific foundation for preschool pedagogy. Nonetheless, an analysis of their publications reveals substantial differences in their approaches and interpretations of the Pavlovian theory.*

Key words: *Pavlovism, preschool education, attachment theory, travelling libraries.*

Science and education in the countries of the Eastern Bloc after the Second World War developed on a relatively similar path, following the model of the USSR, built on a Marxist-Leninist materialist worldview. Various forms of bilateral and multilateral cooperation and mutual exchange were established between them, which also aimed at fostering their rapprochement. The views on raising and educating children, on their physical and mental development, as well as the pedagogical practice itself in the countries of the Eastern Bloc also have similar features. They have been strengthened by the exchange and

cooperation between institutions and scholars in these fields, particularly active since the mid-1960s. Nevertheless, there remained differences due to traditions, the scientific and political environment, as well as biographical background and international contacts of individual scientists.

The article aims to highlight some common features and differences in the first decades of the Cold War by comparing the scientific biographies and views of two women-scientists in Bulgaria and the GDR: Sofia Avramova and Eva Schmidt-Kolmer, who were among the leading figures in child psychology and preschool pedagogy from the second half of the 1940s for several decades. From the beginning of the 1950s, they adopted the Pavlovian teaching as a starting point in their work, and on this basis they carried out considerable experimental work together with their teams. In the 1970s, as leaders and professors in their field, they participated in an international team of Soviet, East German and Bulgarian scientists on the problems of children's adaptation to institutions (nurseries, kindergartens). As a result of this exchange, joint editions were published in German, Bulgarian and Russian.

The comparison between these two leading figures in pedagogy and child psychology in the 1950s – 1970s gives the opportunity to reveal important characteristics and tendencies in science in two Eastern European countries. They held the same or similar political views, being Communists since their early youth and surviving political persecutions. They did their research in a lot of children's institutions with more than 1000 children, which was not possible without the logistic support and the participation of teachers, educators and other staff. In order to reveal in the paper some of the similarities and differences in the way both scholars implemented Pavlovian teachings, the Thomas Popkewitz' concept of 'Travelling Libraries' is used. In his book "Inventing the Modern Self and John Dewey", he explores his concept of "traveling libraries", and the transformation into "indigenous foreigner" in different cultures: a process that depends on the way in which ideas are naturalized and nationalized, whereby each scientific impact is carried out in a specific cultural context.¹

Biographies, interviews, personal documents, publications are used for the purpose of this comparison. There is a dissertation about Eva Schmidt-Kolmer

¹ POPKEWITZ T. (Ed.), *Inventing the Modern Self and John Dewey: Modernities and the Traveling of Pragmatism in Education*, Palgrave Macmillan, 2008.

written by Gabriele Arndt ², and recently there were publications about her research as one of the first scholars in the GDR, who accepted and implemented the attachment theory of John Bowlby in the 1950s. About the activity of Sofia Avramova there are archive documents and publications in pedagogical periodicals from 1999³. There are also published memoirs of the international collaboration: the autobiography of the Bulgarian scholar Anastasiya Atanasova-Vukova (1926 - 2018)⁴ and the Soviet scientist Kseniya Pechora (1926 - 2021),⁵ which are also used as well as documents of the pedagogical institutions.

Biographical Trajectories

Eva Schmidt-Kolmer was born in Vienna in 1913 in an intellectual Jewish family. She studied since 1932 at the Medical Faculty in Vienna and became a member of the Austrian Communist Youth Organization. In 1938 she emigrated to London and after the War together with her husband Heinz Schmidt - also a Communist - she left London for the SBZ, where both became members of the SED. In 1948 – 1950 Eva Schmidt-Kolmer was Secretary of the Democratic Women's Union. After a short period in which the couple was suspected as former emigres in the West not to be politically loyal, they could continue their successful careers. In 1952 Eva Schmidt-Kolmer got a PhD degree. She was assistant professor for School Hygiene at the Leipzig University and later she became Director of the Institute for Child Hygiene and Professor at Humboldt University Berlin. She visited scientific institutions in the Soviet Union and took part in various initiatives of collaboration with Soviet and East European (Bulgarian, Slovak and others) colleagues. She wrote a lot of books about children's development, the influence of the living conditions, and children's education in nurseries and kindergartens ⁶.

² ARNDT G., *Leben und wissenschaftliches Werk Eva Schmidt-Kolmers (25.06.1913 - 29.08.1991)*, Berlin, 2002.

³ ГЕОРГИЕВ Л., София Аврамова, Педагогика, 1999, no. 2, pp.14-18.

⁴ АТАНАСОВА А., *Моята педагогическа изповед*, Шумен, 2016.

⁵ ПЕЧОРА, К. Л., Интервью, Управление ДООУ, 2018, no.5 2018; <https://tc-sfera.ru/teachers/pechora-kseniya-lyutsianovna/>

⁶ SCHMIDT-KOLMER E., *Der Einfluss der Lebensbedingungen auf die Entwicklung des Kindes im Vorschulalter*, Akademie Verlag, 1963; SCHMIDT-KOLMER E., REUMANN J., *Leitfaden fuer die Erziehung in Krippen und Heimen*, Berlin, Verlag Volk und Gesundheit, 1957. SCHMIDT-KOLMER E., *Verhalten und Entwicklung des Kleinkindes*, Akademie Verlag, 1959.

Sofia Avramova was born in 1899 (or 1900) in the small town of Oryachovo in Northern Bulgaria. She studied pedagogy in the 1920s at the Philosophy Faculty in Sofia. In 1919 she became a member of the Bulgarian Communist Youth Organization, and in 1923 – a member of the Bulgarian Communist Party. She was socialized in the Communist movement in the time after 1924 as the Communist Party and all Communist organizations in Bulgaria were prohibited, thus her Communist activity was persecuted as illegal. She took various teaching positions in Sofia but was fired on political reasons. After WWII, as the Fatherland Front led by the Bulgarian Worker's Party (Communist) took the power in Bulgaria, Sofia Avramova was among 15 Communist pedagogues who were recommended to the Ministry of education for leading positions in the national education. She was appointed as lecturer at the Institute for preschool teachers in Sofia. This way her contact with the preschool pedagogy started. At the Institute for Preschool teachers, Sofia Avramova was the key figure in removing the strong American pedagogical and psychological influence claimed to be 'bourgeois' in the late 1940s - beginning of the 1950s, and in establishing the Soviet model. "This environment, together with a planned educational process, will create the new type of child, with a new psyche corresponding to the socialist era..." she wrote in 1950. "This will require, in many cases, some inherited tendencies in children to be suppressed and silenced." It was necessary also to fight against all pedagogical influences.⁷ After the Pavlovian session in 1950, Avramova started an intensive experimental work in kindergartens which continued in the next decades. Sofia Avramova got her PhD degree in 1953 and in 1958 she became Vice-director of the Pedagogical Institute at the Bulgarian Academy of Science. She was one of the first professors for preschool education in Bulgaria. Since 1946 she traveled a lot to the USSR and was in permanent collaboration with Soviet scientists. Sofia Avramova wrote several books based on the Pavlovian teaching about the physical and mental education (and especially the speech education) in the kindergartens.⁸

The biographies of the two women scientists show some significant differences in their background and life path, but also important similarities: they

⁷ АВРАМОВА С., Методи на предучилищното възпитание, Известия на института по педагогика, 1950, no. 1 pp. 193 – 246.

⁸ АВРАМОВА С., Физическото възпитание в детската градина в духа на учението на Иван П. Павлов, С, 1953.

came from close generations, with academic education, they received their scientific degrees at the same time (1952 - 1953) in the scientific and political context of the late Stalinism. What also brings them together is the early and long-term political activity and participation in the communist movement, which was an important career resource in the conditions of the communist regime in East Germany (GDR) and Bulgaria after the end of the Second World War. A common prerequisite for their career was that during the years of their activity, the number of institutions for children: nurseries, kindergartens, children's homes, and others, greatly increased. In the USSR and in Eastern European countries, this was a state policy which, on the one hand, aimed to liberate women as a workforce, and on the other hand, to control the entire process of raising children. The number of children covered by the network of childcare facilities was growing rapidly. The process of institutionalization confronted societies on both sides of the Iron Curtain with questions about the place of parents and the family in general in the care and education of children. The expansion of the network in children's institutions opened up space for professional education and realization of a large number of women employed as teachers, nurses, pediatricians. The scientific and experimental infrastructure in this area, which attracted pediatricians, nurses, pedagogues, psychologists, and other researchers, was also growing. Good opportunities for publications and scientific careers for women were created in this new research field.

Despite the common features, the ideological and scientific context in which the changes and sovietization in the field of pedagogy and psychology in Bulgaria and the GDR took place was not the same. In the GDR, the emphasis was placed above all on overcoming the Nazi legacy, so there was also a return to the pedagogical and psychological traditions and authors from the time of the Weimar Republic. Communication with West German science and with Western science in general also continued, albeit on a smaller scale. In Bulgaria, the aspiration was mainly to eradicate American and generally Western influence in pedagogy and psychology and direct application of Soviet educational and pedagogical models.⁹ The struggle against 'pedology' and its removal (which started in USSR in 1936) was a way to remove other pedagogical and psychological views and methods.

⁹ See for the restructuring of education: ЧИЧОВСКА В. , Политиката срещу просветната традиция, С., 2011.

The Pavlovian session

From June 29 to July 4, 1950 in Moscow, a scientific session of both the Academy of Sciences of the USSR and the Academy of Medical Sciences of the USSR under the title "On the flourishing of the Pavlovian teaching" was held, dedicated to the physiology teachings of Ivan Petrovich Pavlov.¹⁰ According to memories of contemporaries, it was personally conceived by Stalin in 1949, when the 100th anniversary of the famous Russian and Soviet scientist was celebrated.¹¹ 1,400 participants attended the large-scale scientific event in the Soviet capital, 80 of them spoke. The session followed the model of the session of the Agricultural Academy (VASHNIL) held two years earlier, which was dedicated to the teaching of Michurin-Lysenko. As a result of the work of the Pavlov session, a decree was adopted with specific tasks for science and practice, which outlined the transformation of research and teaching practices: to pay attention to research on the physiology and pathology of the higher nervous activity of animals and humans, on the study of the second sig-

¹⁰ Ivan Petrovich Pavlov (1849-1936) was a world-renowned Russian and Soviet physiologist whose achievements were related to the experimental study of the so-called conditioned reflex. Based on his observations, he concluded that the nervous system is the link between the environment and the brain. The entire activity of the nervous system is controlled by the cerebral cortex, which "dictates" over the individual organs. Reflexes he observed, like a mirror, reflect the most complex relations with the external environment, in which the organism enters in the search for food. He came to the conclusion that conditioned reflexes express adaptation to the changing conditions of the surrounding world. Life is an endless adjustment to the influences of the outside world. From here, important conclusions arise both about body policies and about the methods and mechanisms of impact on higher nervous activity, especially on the construction of conditioned reflexes and the use of the conditioned reflex in the overall construction of the personality. In 1904 Pavlov was awarded the Nobel Prize. After the October Revolution, the Soviet government provided favorable conditions for his scientific work, although he didn't expressed sympathy for the new system. A high point in the policy of the authorities towards Pavlov was the holding of the World Physiology Congress in 1935. in Moscow. In his book *Pavlov and the New Man*, the German researcher Torsten Rütting examines the statements of Pavlov's physiology from the point of view of the ideas of "fabrication" of the new man under socialism. The Pavlovian Session of 1950 adopted the organic model of society, seeking the correspondence of the idea of the "dictatorship" of the cerebral cortex with the Stalinist centralist social model. On this basis, any spontaneous, autonomous or self-organizing processes are excluded both in the organism and in society. See RUETING, T., *Pavlov and the New Men: Diskurse über Disciplinierung in Sowjetrussland*, Muenchen: Oldenburg, 2002.

¹¹ ЯРОШЕВСКИЙ, М. Г. Сталинизм и судьбы советской науки: Репрессированная наука. Ленинград: Наука, 1991, pp.6-33. <http://www.ihst.ru/projects/sohist/books/os/9-33.htm>

nal system (speech) and its interactions with the first signal system (senses), the study of the functional relations between the cerebral cortex and internal organs; to revise the university programs, to develop new textbooks on physiology and pathophysiology for universities, for medical, pedagogical and agricultural higher schools and institutes of physical culture, compiled on the main ideas of I. P. Pavlov and the achievements of the domestic (Russian and Soviet) physiology.¹²

This session was part of a series of events in the time of late Stalinism, which placed science under increasingly strict political control, as well as with public stigmatization of scientists and scientific disciplines. It also coincided with other campaigns: against cosmopolitanism and ‘slavish imitations of foreign models’ in science; the campaign to hold the so-called "courts of honor" over scholars;¹³ as well as against ‘formalism’ in art. At the same time, Stalin's series of articles on linguistics, which caused a great response in scientific circles and education, was published¹⁴. Thus, the "Pavlovian session" was not an isolated phenomenon limited to the field of medical sciences. Together with the decisions of the VASHNIL session, it affirmed the thesis of the determining importance of the environment for the development of living organisms and strongly influenced the official philosophical views, the impact of which spread through the institutional path to the entire scientific and educational infrastructure.¹⁵

The importance of the scientific session "On the flourishing of the Pavlovian teaching" has not been overlooked by historical literature. In Bulgarian historiography on the development of science after 1944, this session was also listed without detailing its impact on individual sciences.¹⁶ The decisions of the session greatly affected psychology and preschool pedagogy. This impact was also expressed in the intensified experimental work with children in kindergartens, nurseries, and "Mother and Child" homes. Building conditional

¹² За разцвета на Павловското учение, Материали от научната сесия на АН на СССР и АМН на СССР, посветена физиологичните проблеми от учението на И. П. Павлов, състояла се в Москва от 29 юни до 4 юли 1950 година, София, 1950.

¹³ СОНИН, А. С. Борьба с космополитизмом в советской науке, М., 2011

¹⁴ These articles were immediately translated and published in Bulgarian.

¹⁵ See ЦВЕТАЕВА, Н., Влияние августовской сессии ВАСХНИЛ на педагогике, Владимир, 1999.

¹⁶ See ЖИВКОВА, Н. Усмиряване на разума. Преустройство на БАН 1944 - 1953. София, ИК Гутенберг, 2006.

reflexes and their research was the most widely spread experimental method. This corresponded with a perception of the child as a reflexive being, who responds in a certain way to external irritations and influences, as appropriate conditioned reflexes were built. Hence, autonomous behavior was seen as a deviation, and therefore those disciples of Pavlov or other scientists who dealt with the autonomous and active side of brain processes such as Leon Orbeli or Nikolai Bernstein, were stigmatized by the Pavlovian session. In order to implement the decisions of the session, in 1952 an all-Union conference was held in Moscow on the philosophical questions of the physiology of the Higher Nervous Activity and psychology. The conference reports have been discussed since the fall of 1951. The All-Union Conference on Psychology sharpened the ideological requirements and ensured the dominance of conditional-reflex topics in the works of psychologists. The "viciousness of bourgeois psychological theories" influencing some Soviet scientists was exposed. In these conditions of critics and control, Soviet psychologists reacted differently to the decisions of the session. Some of them adapted by absorbing Pavlovian rhetoric, which almost disappeared as the ideological pressure eased. Others seemed to absorb and apply the official decisions.

The implementation of the decisions of the session coincided with the process of the Sovietization of education and culture in Bulgaria. Georgi Dimitrov's wife, Roza Dimitrova, personally played a strong role in the pre-school transformation. With her support and through the Bulgarian-Soviet societies, Soviet preschool literature quickly entered circulation. A section was opened to the Bulgarian-Soviet association in 1946, using the Soviet term for pre-school education – 'douchilishtno vospitanie'. Translations from Soviet pedagogical manuals, instructions and regulations were issued and put into practice, and special groups of three members of the Bulgarian National Women's Union have been formed to monitor the work of teachers in kindergartens.¹⁷ In 1947-1948, the pressure for total implementation of the Soviet model of preschool education grew. In the book published in 1947 by the Communist philosopher Asen Kiselinchev *Progressive and reactionary ideas in pedagogy*¹⁸, the ideas of pedology - a pedagogical and psychological notion of the child, which primarily respected the children's personality and interests, denounced in the USSR in

¹⁷ See ДИМИТРОВА Р. ,Задачите на тричленките, София, 1946.

¹⁸ КИСЕЛИНЧЕВ, А., Прогресивни и реакционни идеи в педагогиката, С., 1947.

June 1936, as well as the "American school of John Dewey" were discussed in the chapter on reactionary pedagogical ideas alongside racial theories. Pedology was defined as a "pseudoscience"¹⁹. Sofia Avramova published the book *Pre-school education in the view of the Soviet methods*²⁰, the publication being dedicated to the wife of the Bulgarian Communist leader - Rosa Dimitrova.²¹ Again, pedology was accused as reactionary and scholastic, and child psychology was also criticized.²² Maria Montessori's views were qualified as mystical, John Dewey's project method – as 'fundamentally reactionary because built on reactionary psychological premises'.²³ The Soviet manual for educational work in kindergartens was translated in 1948 and started to be applied in these institutions. In 1951 the reports of the conference in the RSFSR on preschool education were also published.²⁴

After the Pavlovian session in Moscow, in both Bulgaria and the GDR similar scientific sessions were prepared. They took place in Bulgaria at the end of 1951 (Sofia) and in the GDR in early 1953 (Leipzig). The Pavlovian approaches caused significant rearrangements in scientific power positions. New pedagogical leaders got opportunities to proclaim the new Pavlovian approaches in their research and to criticise from these positions old school researchers. They also absorbed in their research the terminology of the Pavlovian paradigm and started to do experimental research in this field using Soviet publications about conditional reflexes, type of nervous activity, mobility of nervous processes, interrelations between the first and the second signal systems, etc.

The Attachment Theory

During the 1940s and 1950s, important international discussions in the children's psychology about child development, importance of mother's role,

¹⁹ КИСЕЛИНЧЕВ, А., op. cit. p. 48.

²⁰ АВРАМОВА, С., Предучилищното възпитание с оглед на съветските методи, София, 1947. Before the publication S. Avramova presented a report on the same topic to the "Preschool Education" section at the Bulgarian-Soviet Association. See Аврамова С, op. cit, p. 7.

²¹ Rosa Fleishman-Dimitrova (1896 - 1957), wife of Georgi Dimitrov (1882-1949). The dedication of the book was: "To Comrade Rosa Dimitrova, I thank you from the bottom of my heart for strengthening my faith in the work I had started". Avramova S., op. cit, p.3.

²² See САМОДУМОВ Т., Preface to the book of S. Avramova.

²³ АВРАМОВА С., op. cit. p. 13-17.

²⁴ Доклади на Всероссийската научна конференция по предучилищно възпитание София, 1951.

and the impact of child care institutions on child development started. The most important among them were triggered by René Spitz's theory of hospitalism as well as by the 'attachment theory' of the English psychiatrist John Bowlby, further developed experimentally by Mary Ainsworth. According to John Bowlby's attachment theory, the relationship between the child and the mother in early childhood is crucial for mental and physical development. Deprivation of this closeness leads to serious consequences. Mary Ainsworth carried out a series of experiments that further developed this theory. Hospitalism expressed the negative impact of life in institutions on children's development: weight loss, retardation of physical and mental development.²⁵

In 1952 John Bowlby's book *Maternal Care and Mental Health* was published by the World Health Organization in a French translation and distributed through it throughout the world.²⁶ In order to research the role of the mother and the emotional connection with the child, Bowlby studied the childhood of 44 young thieves, citing also materials from children's institutions - children's homes and nurseries. Deprivation from the mother or from the person who cares (significant adult), according to him, damages the mental health and development of the child.

Attachment theory has sparked a great deal of scientific and public discussion and has fueled experimental work in the field. It has been criticized from a feminist point of view, as a justification for limiting women in the world of motherhood and home. Anna Freud and René Spitz also criticized Bowlby from a Freudian perspective. Later, Bowlby, under the influence of the animal behavior science (Konrad Lorenz), deepened his views on some of the biological prerequisites for the relationship between mother and child, which concepts were also subjected to criticism. In the 1960s and 1970s, attachment theory and hospitalism theory contributed strongly to the deinstitutionalization process that grew in the following decades. These views contributed to changing also the attitude towards children in the family and to its emotionalization.

²⁵ Hospitalism has been a topic of research since the beginning of the twentieth century. In Bulgaria, the term entered the discussions about children in institutions (nurseries) in the early 1930s.

²⁶ See BOWLBY J. , *Soins maternels et Santé Mentale. Contribution of L'Organisation Mondiale de la Santé au program des Nations Unies pour la protection des enfants sans foyer*, Organization Mondiale de la Santé, Palais des Nations, Geneva, 1951. The book was also delivered to the National Library in Sofia, where it was set in a separate catalogue of publications of international organizations.

In socialist countries, the theory of hospitalism and the attachment theory generally found a weak response, although they did not contradict the materialistic thesis of the dominance of the environment in the formation of the child's personality. But this theory appeared at the height of the Cold War, when the reference to Western authors was seen as a manifestation of unwelcome cosmopolitanism. More importantly, at that time in these countries the priority of public education over the family was firmly established. A third reason is related to the focus of attachment theory on the psychological side of children's development, while after the Pavlovian session, it was believed that the physiology of Higher Nervous Activity largely exhausts the tasks of psychology. However, John Bowlby's theory penetrated into some Eastern European countries. In the GDR its spread was due to the publications of Eva Schmidt-Kolmer. The attachment theory was spread to West Germany as well. Psychiatrist and psychotherapist Annemarie Dürsen (1916 – 1998) introduced it to discussions in West Germany. In 1958 she published studies of children in homes, comparing them to children in foster care. This study contributed to the deinstitutionalization of nursing homes in West Germany. Eva Schmidt-Kolmer also knew and cited her works; probably the two scientists knew personally each other.

Experimental work and scientific views of Eva Schmidt-Kolmer

Eva Schmidt-Kolmer was among the first East German scholars to introduce attachment theory and hospitalism theory in East Germany by using in her experimental work central concepts and approaches and combining them with the Pavlovian teaching's approach. Thus, with her work, she created a remarkable dialogue between scientific schools. In recent years, interest in her work has grown in connection with the issue of the spread of Bowlby's ideas in Eastern Europe.²⁷

In her book on the behavior and development of the young child, published in 1959, Eva Schmidt-Kolmer summarized her experimental work with 1,768 children by combining some basic Pavlovian constructs with John Bowlby's attachment theory.²⁸ As one of the first scientists in the GDR to present Bowl-

²⁷ BERTH, F. , A Comparison Across the Iron Curtain. Continuities and Discontinuities of Residential Care in the Two German States, *Balkanistic Forum*, 2024, no. 3, p. 122-135; HENSCHEL F., Red Bowlby: Attachment Theory in Socialist Czechoslovakia: *Historie – Otázky – Problémy*, 2023, no.1, p. 56 – 71.

²⁸ SCHMIDT-KOLMER, E., Verhalten und Entwicklung des Kleinkindes, Der Einfluss verschiedenartigen sozialen Milieus auf das kindliche Verhalten und seine Bedeutung fuer die Hygiene des Kindesalters Akademie Verlag, 1959. Cf. also: SCHMIDT-KOLMER, E., Der Einfluss der Lebensbedingungen auf die Entwicklung des Kindes im Vorschulalter, Akademie Verlag, 1963 ; SCHMIDT-KOLMERE., REUMANN, J., Leitfaden fuer die Erziehung in Krippen und Heimen, Berlin, Verlag Volk und Gesundheit, 1957.

by's ideas in the scientific literature, the experimental work was built on the comparison of the development of three groups of children: living with family (observed through child consulting centre), in day nurseries and in closed institutions for children. It was based on the Pavlovian concept of the decisive role of the environment in human development and the interrelationship between the surrounding world and the higher nervous activity, assuming that behavior is the result of creating and confirming so called 'temporary nerve connections' – the conditioned reflexes.²⁹ The research methodology included a description of movement reactions, emotional reactions (smile) and speech development of children. Physiological aspects of development were essential, especially the interaction between subcortical and cortical activity of infants. The infant's activity was still determined by subcortical rhythm, and only with the differentiation of cortical activity, especially with the inhibition process, the selective nature of the irradiation of nervous processes and the specification of behavioral features arose.³⁰ Brain development must have reached a certain stage of differentiation to be able to respond, and then the properties became fixed and only a limited response could be made. Eva Schmidt-Kolmer connected the Soviet concepts on the phase development of reflex forms (Volokhov), the concepts of William Stern on the fast and slow phases of mental development, and the views of the Czech scientists Hahn and Krecek on the critical phases of development, considering speech development as a good example. She also quoted John Bowlby about the role of the mother in those phases when a certain development was in progress. Eva Schmidt-Kolmer observed the child's behavior towards the significant adult and the reactions of smiling.³¹ In accordance with Pavlov, she connected these reactions with the orientation reflex: when the environment changed, the senses became activated and directed to a new source of the irritation. The main emphasis was placed on children smiling as a very important indication of contact with the adult. Smiling as an indicator was taken up by Bowlby, but Eva Schmidt-Kollmer also explored it in its conditioned-reflexive nature. In the comparison between the three groups

²⁹ SCHMIDT-KOLMER E. , Verhalten und Entwicklung...p. 14

³⁰ Op. cit., p. 15.

³¹ Op. cit., p. 19-20.

of children - family, crèche, institution - her conclusions were that the children from the weekly nursery lag behind in motor reactions, as well as in communication and speech reactions, and in social homes all reactions were delayed, especially speech.³² Here she made her main conclusion that the propiate nutrition and care are not enough for normal physical and mental development of most of the children. The deficite of emotional connection to a certain adult, the lack of communication, the insufficient organization of diverse activities and contact with the surrounding world limit the development of children. An important conclusion was also that children from the social homes show a weakness of the cortical processes and a strong dominance of the subcortical processes: these children cannot concentrate, their hands tremble when they have to do something more complicated, they get tired easily; they are not able to readjust to changes. The balance between the nervous processes of excitation and inhibition is disturbed (according to Pavlov, this balance is of fundamental importance), they often sleep with open eyes. She observed outbursts of anger and affects, as well as stereotyped movements, nodding, head banging – all this shows the dominance of subcortical processes. To a much lesser extent, these phenomena were characteristic of day nurseries.³³ Discussing in her texts with the Soviet physiologist Levon Orbeli, the psychologist Alexander Luria, and the behaviorist R. Shaffer, Eva Schmidt-Kolmer emphasized the physiological features of insufficient cortical activity, insufficient internal inhibition due to insufficient afferent connections. She believed that all of this is of great importance to mental development, referring to Bowlby that after prolonged stay in social homes an isolated personality type develops, incapable of attachment, with poor concentration and a weak need to fit in the community. "Every child needs a strong emotional bond for their normal development in their first years, which can only develop if there is a loving attachment from a trusted adult," she wrote.³⁴ Not only did the regime create stability of living conditions for the child, which provide constant frameworks, not so much age-appropriate care and nutrition, but above all the constancy of the main environmental factor for the child was created by the significant adult.³⁵ This requires speech development through systematic talking to the child and individual communication

³² Op. cit., p. 130.

³³ Op. cit., p. 131.

³⁴ Op. cit., p. 132.

³⁵ Op. cit.

with each individual child.³⁶ In another book of hers - a guide to education in nurseries and homes, published in this period, Eva Schmidt-Kolmer emphasizes that it is especially important to create joy for children in weekly nurseries and homes. They need tenderness, holding in hands and being talked to.³⁷

In August 1961 the Second international congress on mental retardation took place in Vienna. Eva Schmidt-Kolmer presented her contribution on early children's hospitalism as a cause of the so-called "pseudo debility"³⁸ based on her experimental work with about 1000 children up to 6 years old. She confirmed that children, especially at preschool age, need a close, long-term connection, an active life under the guidance of an adult. In children from social homes, the processes of excitation and inhibition were delayed, sensorimotor abilities and skills were greatly behind. The development of speech began significantly later, and the vocabulary was significantly less, as well as the abilities to distinguish colors, to count, etc. About 30% of the children in the homes shown a delay in preschool age and about 50% of them had to go to an auxiliary school. These were children without organic disabilities, but they gave a picture of debility due to insufficient stimulation of brain activity.³⁹ The topic of 'pseudo debility' was also advocated by other authors at the congress, and Eva Schmidt-Kolmer's observations fit into the discussion on it.

Based on the conclusions of her research, Eva Schmidt-Kolmer pleaded for changes in the attitude and upbringing of children in institutions. This was emphasised in her nursery and kindergarten guides and textbooks.

Experimental work and views of Sofia Avramova

During the period 1950-1957 Sofia Avramova, who at that time was the deputy director of the Institute of Pedagogy at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, also led a significant experimental activity in kindergartens in the country. In the early 1950s, she published two books: *Education and training in the native language in the kindergarten in the spirit of the work of J.V. Stalin*

³⁶ Op. cit., p. 135.

³⁷ SCHMIDT-KOLMER, E. REUMANN, J., Leitfaden fuer die Erziehung in Krippen und Heimen, Verlag Volk und Gesundheit Berlin, 1957, p. 105-107.

³⁸ SCHMIDT-KOLMER, E., Fruehkindlicher Hospitalismus als Ursache von Pseudodebilitaet, in: Second International Congress on Mental Retardation, Wien, 1961, Vol. II, pp. 188-195.

³⁹ SCHMIDT-KOLMER, E., Op. cit.

*"Marxism and questions of linguistics" and the teachings of I. P. Pavlov*⁴⁰ and together with Elena Taseva *Physical education in kindergarten in the spirit of the teachings of I. P. Pavlov*⁴¹. In their book on physical education, Sofia Avramova and Elena Taseva referred to the Pavlovian scientists - Anatolij Ivanov-Smolensky, Ivan Krasnogorsky, as well as other Soviet authors on conditioned reflexes. Their work was based entirely on the concept of the nervous activity as a response to external irritations: "The activity of the cortex of the large hemispheres is a higher nervous activity, because through it the more perfect adaptation, balancing of the organism with the surrounding external world is realized," they wrote.⁴² The purpose of physical education was to build in children motor habits and automatization of movements as complex chain of conditioned reflexes.⁴³ "After the repetition of given movements in the same form and connection, in the cortex of the brain the excitation got concentrated in certain brain centers."⁴⁴

At the end of the 1950s, Sofia Avramova published her book about teaching the mother tongue in kindergarten.⁴⁵ Her experiments followed the settings of the Soviet researcher A. P. Usova for the native language in kindergarten. Her experiments were entirely based on building conditioned reflexes. „The formation and development of children’s speech implies the construction and strengthening of a number of connections in the cortex of the large hemispheres. Conditioned reflexes are produced through the first and second signal systems. The work of the second signal system (language) determines the development of the child's higher nervous activity, the formation of his mental processes."⁴⁶ The first signal system - senses, visual thinking directly reflects the external environment, and through language, ideas and thoughts get an external expression. Through the conditioned reflex activity of the cortex of the

⁴⁰ АВРАМОВА, С., Възпитание и обучение по родния език в детската градина в духа на труда на Й. В. Сталин „Марксизмът и въпросите на езикознанието“ и учението на И. П. Павлов, София, БАН, 1953.

⁴¹ АВРАМОВА С., ТАСЕВА Е.. Физическото възпитание в детската градина в духа на учението на И П. Павлов, София, БАН, 1953.

⁴² Op. cit., p.7.

⁴³ Op. cit. p.14.

⁴⁴ Op. cit. p.15.

⁴⁵ АВРАМОВА, С., КОЗАРЕВ, Г., МИХАЙЛОВА, П., Обучението по родния език в детската градина и умственото претоварване. Изучавания на висшата нервна дейност на децата от предучилищна възраст : Експериментални изследвания, С., 1958.

⁴⁶ Op. cit., p. 3.

large hemispheres, the interaction with the external environment is reflected by the child. In order to master the language, the child needs special training, correct grammatical speech: "it is necessary, through purposeful and organized observations and through repetition, to strengthen the temporary connections ...And with the second signal system, there is the construction of temporary conditional connections, only here the words became objective signals, irritants..."⁴⁷ In children, a basic well-established stereotype of a correct sentence must be built - a complete sentence with the correct word order, observing a certain sequence.⁴⁸ In the following years, Sofia Avramova worked together with the psychologist Ema Geron⁴⁹, conducting experiments in kindergartens. They studied the associations triggered by the use of different words, viewing the associations as conditioned reflexes.⁵⁰

The comparison of the attitude towards the Pavlovian teaching of the two researchers - Eva Schmidt-Kolmer and Sofia Avramova shows that both researchers rely on their experimental work with children in the 1950s on the Pavlovian teaching in harmony with the official scientific policy of that period. This is an important unifying moment that creates prerequisites for dialogue between scientists in Eastern European countries and the USSR. The research questions they ask regarding children were different: Eva Schmidt-Kolmer was interested primarily in the development of children (mainly developmental psychology), and Sofia Avramova – in their physical and mental education and training. Although in different ways, both were interested in the development of speech in children and the influence and role of the adult. Relying on the Pavlovian teaching, Eva Schmidt-Kolmer found points of contact with

⁴⁷ АВРАМОВА, С., Обучението по родния език в детската градина, в: АВРАМОВА, С., КОЗАРЕВ, Г., МИХАЙЛОВА, П., Обучението по родния език в детската градина и умственото претоварване. Изучавания на висшата нервна дейност на децата от предучилищна възраст : Експериментални изследвания, София., 1958.р. 7-8.

⁴⁸ Op. cit. p. 38-40.

⁴⁹ Ema Geron (1920-2011) was a leading Bulgarian psychologist, professor at the National Sport Academy in Sofia. In 1973 she emigrated together with her husband Peter Semerdzhiev for political reasons in Israel where she became professor in Tel Aviv. Her associates in Sofia came under political suspicion in the next years. Sofia Avramova was affected by this political distrust due to her close collaboration with Ema Geron.

⁵⁰ Вж. АВРАМОВА С., ГЕРОН Е. и др., Система на нравственото възпитание в детската градина, С., 1970. About the experiments in the kindergartnes see also ПОПОВА К. , Висшата нервна дейност на социализма. Революционното приложение на една кучешка слюнка в предучилищното възпитание през 1950-те години, в: КОЛЕВА Д. (Съст.), Тялото при социализма: режими и репрезентации, София, 2016, С. 19-38.

a number of other authors from different schools in the field of research on child development. For her, conditioned reflexes were an important moment in child development, but she embedded their building in accordance with the phases of development and the necessary favorable factors for this, depending on the emotional ties with the mother or another significant adult. Physiological development was also dependent on the psychological interaction with the child. For Sofia Avramova, institutions have a leading role for children. She was interested in brain physiological processes, but not in the psychological aspects of children's physical and speech development. Rather, she looked for the disciplining opportunities for the development of the body and of speech and language, where, according to her, the role of creating conditioned reflexes and the automation of reactions is. The relationship between physiology and speech education was perceived as direct based on the building of conditional reflexes.

At that time, another researcher, who was much closer in her approach to Eva Schmidt-Kolmer, was working in the field of children's speech research in Bulgaria. This was the psychologist and pedagogue Vasilka Manova-Tomova (1912-1976). Her publications and scientific contacts, as well as the research of her collaborators, were the bridge between the institutions of Eva Schmidt-Kolmer and Sofia Avramova and provided the basis for cooperation between research groups in the GDR, Bulgaria and the USSR in the late 1960s and early 1970s.

Vasilka Manova-Tomova graduated in pedagogy from Sofia University and collaborated with prof. Dimitar Katsarov in his experimental work on children's intelligence, which was the main trend in child psychology in the interwar period in Bulgaria. Prof. Katsarov, a Swiss graduate, was a supporter of the free education and the main representative of Bulgaria in the League for Free Education, thus he was close to the views of pedology. Together with Dr. Efrem Beldedov, he initiated intelligence research according to the Binet-Simon tests. For this purpose, he founded a laboratory where he attracted young scholars such as Gencho Piriyov, Vasilka Manova and others. In 1942, as a lecturer at the Institute for Kindergarten Teachers in Sofia, Vasilka Manova-Tomova published a textbook "Lectures on child research", in which she briefly explained the methods of observation and tests for child development⁵¹, on which she worked with Katsarov. She also contributed to the magazine "Our Child", issued by the Union for the Child Protection in Bulgaria.

⁵¹ МАНОВА-ТОМОВА, В. Лекции по изследване на детето, С., 1942.

After the establishment of the Communist regime in Bulgaria, Dimitar Katsarov and his school of pedagogy were viewed with distrust. Insofar as they were loyal to the new regime, they were not subjected to political repression, but their views were sharply criticized in the philosophical and pedagogical press and in scientific forums.⁵² In 1945, at the Institute for Kindergarten Teachers, Sofia Avramova managed to attract Vasilka Manova to membership in the Communist Party, but a bit later Vasilka Manova-Tomova left the party. This step increased the political distrust towards her. After a period of criticism, she left the institute, for some time she worked in the Ministry of Public Health, and then - until her death - in the Institute of Motherhood and Childhood (later Institute of Pediatrics). Here, Vasilka Manova-Tomova focused on the study of children's development during early childhood and elaborated her own system of assessment of this development, which was introduced and used in childcare facilities. At the end of the 1950s and in the 1960s, similarly to Eva Schmidt-Kolmer, she made comparative studies of the development of children in families, nurseries and children's homes.

According to the memories of her close colleague Anastasia Atanasova, "My Pedagogical Confession"⁵³, Vasilka Manova shared with her that "massively, the children in the nursery and the Mother and Child Home were catastrophically lagging behind in the development of speech, and this reflected on their overall mental development."⁵⁴ In her further research in the 1960s and 1970s, Vasilka Manova-Tomova emphasized that the further away from the family children were raised, the more backwardness and difficulties were experienced in their development. Here she also referred to the research of Eva Schmidt-Kolmer, as well as the Soviet psychologists S. Rubinstein, Lev Vygotsky, Nina Aksarina and others.⁵⁵ She concluded: "Since the need to use childcare facilities will increase, it is necessary to create an increasingly close connection and mutual penetration of the advantages of the family environment - greater individualization and emotionalization of the relationship with the children in the nursery, and from daycare to transfer to the family more

⁵² See ТЕРЗИЙСКА, М., Димитър Кацаров и движението за ново възпитание, С., 2013.

⁵³ АТАНАСОВА, А., Моята педагогическа изповед, Шумен, 2016.

⁵⁴ *Op. cit.*, p. 27.

⁵⁵ МАНОВА-ТОМОВА, В., Влиянието на средата в семейството и в детските заведения върху психическото развитие на децата, в: ЛЮТОВ А. (Ред.), Жената. Труд и бит, С., 1977, Издателство на БАН, с.315 – 332.

targeted requirements for children and a more systematic and methodical creation of skills and habits."⁵⁶ A decade after Schmidt-Kolmer, Manova-Tomova confirmed her conclusions: "early, prolonged separation of the child from the family environment is not conducive to its mental development and damages the state of his nervous system."⁵⁷

During the period 1968-1973 Manova-Tomova researched the movements, sensory activity, emotional-social behavior and speech of children until the end of the third year - in a family, in day nurseries, in weekly nurseries with a predominant importance of a nursery environment and in a closed nursery without contact with the family. She used the psychodiagnostic method she developed. The main difference, according to her, came from the frequency and emotional saturation in the relationship with the children, which cannot be reproduced in any childcare facility.⁵⁸ Although in the current nurseries, according to her, "there is no more 'hospitalism' - grayness and monotony of the environment, which led the children to boredom, to constant whining, rolling on the floor and sucking their fingers ... they lack something to fully equal the children raised in a good family environment. This applies particularly to the development of emotions and speech, which are known to be particularly important aspects of mental development during early childhood."⁵⁹

The publication of her conclusions characterized the changed atmosphere at that time in psychology. In the 1960s and 1970s, Soviet psychology rediscovered Lev Vygotsky and other Soviet psychologists who had been silenced for a long time, thus pedagogy began to be psychologized, the individual was discovered as an object of study, some Western authors began to be cited: Jean Piaget, Hans Selye and others. In 1969 a research group of Vasilka Manova-Tomova, Sofia Avramova and Anastasia Atanasova began to explore the transition between day nurseries and kindergartens, which was a research topic also in USSR and other East European countries. In search of cooperation in this research, in the following years the three countries - the USSR, the GDR and Bulgaria (the Department of Physiology, Development and Education of Children at the Central Teachers Institute - USSR - Moscow, the Institute of Child and Adolescent Hygiene - Berlin and the Institute of Pediatrics in Sofia) united

⁵⁶ Op. cit., p.332.

⁵⁷ ДИНКОВА, М., Отпусъкът по майчинство – практика и проблеми, в: ЛЮТОВ А. (Ред.), Жената. Труд и бит, С., Издателство на БАН, с.347 – 361.

⁵⁸ МАНОВА-ТОМОВА, В., Влиянието ...

⁵⁹ Op. cit. , p.330-331.

their scientific work on the research topic of the social adaptation of children of early and preschool age.⁶⁰

"Social Adaptation" as a uniting East- European research project in the 1970s

The long-term studies of children in institutions, and of interactions between the child and his environment, the long-term focus on the importance of conditioned reflexes in this relationship and the awareness of the deficits in the perception of the child as a reflecting organism, the freer communication with international science at the end of the 1960s: all this led researchers to search for new approaches to the question of this interaction. These new approaches had to be ideologically acceptable, remaining in the field of socialist science, but also taking into account new international trends.

The publications of Jean Piaget, Hans Selye and others gave impulses to the research of the human adaptation to the social environment. The term of social adaptation emerged as an appropriate research topic and became an important problem in child psychology and pedagogy in the next two decades and contributed to their renewal in Eastern Europe. Nina Aksarina (1899 - 1979) is believed to be the first researcher of social adaptation upon admission to a children's institution in Soviet psychology. Adaptation made it possible to renew the approaches inherited from the Pavlovian teaching, without breaking with them. It became possible to study physiological aspects and processes of the central nervous system, but to put the psychological and social components in the foreground. In Bulgaria, this topic also found a wide public response, especially with the spread of the most popular television series in the 1980s - "Adaptation", dedicated to the everyday life in a psychiatric clinic.

Thus, in the center of the research cooperation in the psychological-pedagogical field between the three teams from USSR, the GDR and Bulgaria in the 1970s, the topic of children's adaptation to the institutions was explored.⁶¹ This project gathered in a common team Sofia Avramova, Vasilka Manova-Tomova, Anastasia Atanasova-Vukova (PRB), Eva Schmidt-Kolmer, Christa Grosh, Jo-

⁶⁰ АТАНАСОВА А. (ред.), Социалната адаптация на децата при постъпване в детските ясли и детски градини, София, 1979, р. 9.

⁶¹ SCHMIDT-KOLMER E. , (Hg.), Soziale Adaptation der Kinder bei der Aufnahme in Einrichtungen der Vorschuerziehung, Volk und Gesundheit, Berlin, 1979, 191 pp.

han Neumann, Maria Seidel (GDR), Raisa Tonkova-Yampolska, Lidiya Golubeeva, Galina Gridneva (USSR) and others.⁶²

In the center of attention of the East German team were the forms of organization of the life of three-year-old children in nurseries and kindergartens. The Bulgarians studied the peculiarities of speech development in the adaptation period and the development of methods to prevent the arrest of speech development.

The research resulted in joint editions in the three languages in 1977-1979. In the foreword of the joint edition, the Western theories in the research area of adaptation were also presented. Here, albeit very briefly, the views of John Bowlby, Anna Freud, René Spitz, Mary Ainsworth, Annemarie Duersen, Ursula Lehr and other Western authors were critically read.⁶³ The critical analysis gave insight into discussions about attachment theory (unknown to Bulgarian readers at this time). It was emphasized that the development of children in institutions was not hindered by the lack of a mother, but by the lack of emotional connection.⁶⁴ The difference between ‘maternal deprivation’ and ‘maternal separation’ was stressed, with the conclusion that separation from the mother did not significantly affect the development of children.⁶⁵ "The negative consequences of the upbringing of children during infancy and early age in closed childcare facilities are not the result of a lack of maternal attitude, but are the result of insufficient emotional contacts and joint activity of the child with adults, as well as insufficient sensory and social stimulation."⁶⁶

At the same time, together with the joint book of the international team on the adaptation, an edition of the Bulgarian part of the group was also published in Bulgaria. It was dedicated to the continuity between family, nurseries and kindergartens.⁶⁷ Based on comparative studies of children from nurseries and children from families, the book echoes the research of Eva Schmidt-Kolmer and Vasilka Tomova. The attention was again placed on the problem

⁶² АТАНАСОВА А. (ред.), Социалната адаптация на децата при постъпване в детските ясли и детски градини, С., 1979, 216 p., a joint edition with ‘Медицина’ – Москва and Volk und Gesundheit – Berlin.

⁶³ АТАНАСОВА А. (ред.), Социалната адаптация, p. 25-28.

⁶⁴ Op. cit., p. 28.

⁶⁵ Op. cit., p. 28.

⁶⁶ Op. cit., p. 25.

⁶⁷ МАНОВА, В., АВРАМОВА, С., АТАНАСОВА А., Приемственост във възпитанието на децата между семейството, детските ясли и детската градина, С., 1979.

of children's adaptation to the institution, emphasizing its materialistic nature: according to the philosophical views of Friedrich Engels, but also of the physiologists Pavlov, Vedensky and Sechenov, adaptation had to be an universal phenomenon.⁶⁸ The role of conditioned reflexes and the construction of a "dynamic stereotype" as a system of conditioned reflexes was again emphasized⁶⁹, and Hans Selye was criticized for neglecting the role of the nervous system in his psychological research. Regarding the balance between family and institutional care for children, the book did not give a definite answer: "Modern living conditions require a large number of children from the earliest age to be raised and educated outside the family - in children's institutions. In many cases, nurseries are the first step and the first connection of a child's social and family education. The small child naturally has the need to live in his family, but the education of the modern man, of the socialist worker, would be carried out too limited and one-sided only within the framework of family education."⁷⁰ And further: "Due to the serious disturbances that occur in the behavior of small children when they are separated from the family when they enter the nursery, modern pedagogical and pediatric science and practice are faced with a number of questions related to the adaptation of children to the demands of the new environment'.⁷¹

Western theories were given much less space here than in the international team's edition. It is obvious that the more extensive exposition of John Bowlby's attachment theory, of Mary Ainsworth experiments, the views of Anna Freud and the other authors in the joint book, was a contribution of the East German group led by Eva Schmidt-Kolmer. The Bulgarians did not take the opportunity to expand the discussion about the adaptation with the Bulgarian readers. Therefore, Bulgarian scientists, psychologists, teachers, and parents only encountered the 'attachment theory' more thoroughly in the 1990s.⁷²

At the time when the two books were published, Vasilka Tomova and Sofia Avramova were no longer alive. The books were finished and prepared for printing by their collaborator Anastasia Atanasova.

⁶⁸ Op. cit., p. 9.

⁶⁹ Op. cit, p. 16-17.

⁷⁰ Op. cit, p. 27.

⁷¹ Op. cit p. 28.

⁷² АЛЕКСИЕВА, Е., Привързаността в живота на човека, студия, ч.1, Годишник на СУ, 1998, no. 91.

Conclusions:

Sofia Avramova and Eva Schmidt-Kolmer were influential scientists in high positions in their field for about three decades. They were socialized as scientists in the conditions of the Cold War, using both their party political advantages and the opportunities for realization in the field of pedagogy and psychology in the conditions of the growing institutionalization of child care and scientific research. After the Pavlovian session in Moscow in 1950, they both adopted Pavlovian teaching as the starting point of their experimental work.

Beyond the ideological and political pressures of the Cold War, Eva Schmidt-Kolmer mobilized resources of different scientific schools in psychology, physiology and pedagogy, using their compatibility: Pavlovian teaching, behaviorism, attachment theory, hospitalism theory and others. She examined the conditioned reflexes of the Pavlovian teaching from the point of view of children's emotional contact, examining its reactions and especially the smile as an indicator of the emotional connection. She also used Pavlovian constructs of the balance between irritation and inhibition to discover the effects of the lack of emotional connections on the dynamics of these processes, and the dominance of subcortical activity in institutionalized children. In order to avoid damage to the child's development in nurseries and children's homes, according to her, the children's institution should be closer the family as an emotional environment.

Sofia Avramova's experimental and scientific work in kindergartens in the 1950s was also in the framework of the Pavlovian session's decisions. For her, children's institutions had a leading role, and the influence of the family had to be weakened. She was primarily interested in the physical and linguistic education of children from the point of view of their physical and mental discipline and the establishment of a correct pattern and order set from above as a purposeful construction of conditioned reflexes in children.

Despite its deficits, the comparison makes it possible to point out some basic similarities and differences in the development of child psychology and pedagogy and the perception of Pavlovian teaching in the early 1950s in the GDR and Bulgaria in the same conditions of the Cold war as well as in similar political pressure to apply the decisions of the scientific session in Moscow in 1950.

Both Eva Schmidt-Kolmer's and Sofia Avramova's research was based on materialistic concepts about the interaction between humans and environment, about the importance of the nervous system as uniting the organism to the

environment and coordinating the other systems, about the balance between the nervous processes of excitation and inhibition, and about the importance of conditioned reflexes. Both of them cited the main Soviet authors : Ivan P. Pavlov, Ivan Krasnogorsky, Anatolij Ivanov-Smolensky, Nina Aksarina and many others. Eva Schmidt-Kolmer 's research deployed Pavlovian teaching in a much wider context of pre-war research and Western authors – above all John Bowlby, Anna Freud, William Stern, the Austrian psychologists Charlotte Buehler and Hildegard Hetzer as well as Anemarie Dührssen. All these authors were rejected (or unknown) in Bulgaria, where the pedagogy and psychology in the new regime started with a strong struggle against Western influence. This hindered for the first decades the introduction and adoption of new ideas, research methods and reduced the discussions and the implementation of new practices in children's institutions despite of the further exchange and the common international projects in the 1970s.

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